

Students' Perception of Guidance and Counselling Services as Correlate of Educational Adjustment, Vocational Choice and Socio-personal Behaviours in Demonstration Secondary School Zaria, Kaduna State

Iro, Babangida Ph.D.

Tel: +2348033540469

irobabangida@gmail.com; biro@noun.edu.ng

Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to assess Students' Perception of Guidance and Counselling Services as Correlate of Educational Adjustment, Vocational Choice and Socio-personal Behaviours in Demonstration Secondary School Zaria, Kaduna State- This research used a cross-sectional descriptive design. Stratified random sampling technique was employed in the collection of data. The total number of senior secondary school students used was 743 out of which 77 were used as a sample of the study. Ten percent of the total student population from each selected class was used in the study. Student's Perception Questionnaire (Researcher Designed) was used to collect data and Kruskal Wallis Test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used and analyzed the relationship among the variables. Although there was no statistically significant relationship between perception and students' educational adjustment, there was however a weak linear statistically significant relationship between students' perception of school guidance and counselling services and their vocation/career choice, and socio-personal behaviour. The study concludes that emphasis appears to be more towards the students' vocational adjustment followed by their personal social adjustment, and least of all, their educational adjustment. The study further recommends that balanced school guidance and counselling service should be used to equally focus on all three aspects of school guidance and counseling.

Keywords: Perception, Guidance and Counselling, Educational Adjustment, Vocational Choice and Socio-personal Behaviours

Introduction

In Nigeria, the history of modern counselling is traced back to vocational guidance given to final year students. Ipaye (2015) sees guidance as a generic label, an umbrella term that covers all the means whereby an institution identifies and responds to the needs of pupils or students no matter the nature of the need and no matter its sources thereby helping the child to develop to his/her maximum potential. The specialists gave career talks on their professions and in the end, a good number of the students were able to select good jobs and/or good careers in their choice of higher institutions (Akinade, et al 2005). They added that

between 1962 when Ibadan career Council was formed and 1967, a greater awareness was created all over the country about career masters and mistresses who collated and disseminated career information to students in their schools across the country. State Ministries of Education also became involved and encouraged the appointment of career officers in schools.

Currently, there appears to be less emphasis and support for guidance in secondary schools, with a reduction of guidance and counselling time. There is also paucity of qualified counsellors to pilot secondary school guidance services. Secondary school owners, where school guidance services exist, convert classroom

teachers to serve as guidance counsellors. These have impacted negatively on the role and work of the guidance counsellor and on the effectiveness of guidance programmes. (Dabone et al 2015). Today the essence of guidance and counselling cannot be over emphasized, the society need guidance and counselling, so the federal government has inserted the need for guidance and counselling courses in our schools in its national policy on education (2004), this has helped to make all the state governors to establish guidance and counselling units in their ministries of education in addition to the counselling units in the university. (Ipa; 2015).

In study carried out by Dabone, Graham and Fabea (2015) found that students who were exposed to guidance and counselling in an experimental model had better academic performance than they had prior to the exposure. This was corroborated by Eyo, Joshua, and Esuong (2010) when they carried out a study on the attitude of secondary school students towards guidance and counselling services in Cross River State in Calabar. However, Mehmood, Rashid, and Azeem (2011) found no statistically significant impact in academic performance of students exposed to guidance and counselling treatment and those who were not exposed to same treatment. They however noted that the mean score of the experimental group of students was higher than the control group. (Mehmood, Rashid, & Azeem, 2011) This meant that although not statistically significant, guidance and counselling services helped improve the students' academic performance.

In another study Babatunde and Osakinle (2013) found that group career guidance and counselling techniques helped improve the vocational maturity of students. In the same vein, Eliamani, Peter, and Richard (2015) found that there was a

statistically significant relationship between access to guidance and counselling services and students' attitude towards studies, as well as career choice of secondary school students in Uganda. (Eliamani et al., 2015)

Never the less Gatua, Sindabi and Chepcheng (2015) in their study found that rural schools indicated high level of impact of guidance and counselling services where female students expressed higher level of behaviour modification in social and emotional adjustment. This led them to conclude that guidance and counselling services in secondary schools helped in modifying students' behaviour in social and emotional adjustments. (Gatua et al., 2015). Gatua (2014) earlier had similar findings as above. Ibrahim, Aloka, Wambiya, and Raburu (2014) also had similar findings. Lack of effective guidance and counseling services may hinder students' adjustment, as such, it could be inferred that school guidance and counselling positively impacted on students' personal and social adjustment.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their educational adjustment.
2. To find out the significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their vocation/career choice.
3. To assess the significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their socio-personal behaviour.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their educational adjustment.
2. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance

and counselling services and their vocation/career choice.

3. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their socio-personal behaviour.

Methodology

This research used a cross-sectional descriptive design. The research is a cross-sectional descriptive study because it studies and describes the characteristics of the study population at a particular point in time. The population size is a total number of 743 senior secondary school students out of which a Sample of 77 students were used by using Stratified random sampling technique. Ten percent of the total student population from each selected class was used in the study. According to Kasomo (2007), 10% of the accessible population is enough in descriptive studies. The instrument used to obtain data was the Questionnaire (researcher defined) which enabled the researchers to find out the students' opinion and ideas on the subject matter. The questions designed by the researcher were basically of closed end questionnaire which gives the respondents sets of alternatives whereby the respondents were allowed to choose the answer.

Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their educational adjustment.

Table 1: Relationship Between Perception of Guidance and Counselling (G&C) and Educational Adjustment of students

Variables	Perception of G&C	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal wallis test	df	Asymp. Sig.
Relationship on educational adjustment	Very poor perception	1	1.00	3.992	3	2.262
	Poor perception	18	36.64			
	Good perception	41	41.27			
	Very good perception	17	38.26			
	Total	77				

The analysis in Table 1 reveals that there is no statistically significant

The validity of the instrument was determined by presenting the questionnaire to an expert in psychology and counselling from National Open University of Nigeria and tested its validity and made necessary corrections on both content and face validity. The data collected was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha procedure to determine the reliability of the instrument and the scale was found to be suitable for this study. Frequency, simple percentage and mean were used to analyze the demographic characteristics of the respondent. In addition, Kruskal Wallis Test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used in analyzing the relationship among the variables. Figures 1-3 analyzed and interpreted Age, Class and level of perception distribution of the Respondents. Figure 4 and 5 analyzed and interpreted the impact of School Guidance and Counselling services on the students' educational adjustment and Students' socio-personal behavior. In addition, Tables 1-3 analyzed and interpreted the impact between student's perception of Guidance and Counselling services on Educational Adjustment, Vocation/Career Choice, and Socio-Personal Behaviour.

relationship between perception of G&C and educational adjustment (Kruskal Wallis test =

3.992, $p = 0.262$). This reveals that although the students generally had a good perception and impact on educational adjustment, both variables were not significantly statistically

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their vocation/career choice.

Table 2: Relationship Between Perception of Guidance and Counselling (G&C) and Vocation/Career Choice of students

Variables	Perception of G&C	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal wallis test	Df	Asymp. Sig.
Relationship on vocation/career choice	Very poor perception	1	1.50	8.801	3	0.032*
	Poor perception	18	29.89			
	Good perception	41	42.20			
	Very good perception	17	43.15			
	Total	77				

The figures in Table 2 shows that there is statistically significant relationship between perception and impact on vocation/career choice (Kruskal Wallis test = 8.801, $p = 0.032$). Further analysis revealed a weak linear relationship between both

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between students' perception of guidance and counselling services and their socio-personal behaviour.

Table 3: Ranking of the Relationship Between Perception of Guidance and Counselling (G&C) and Socio-Personal Behaviour of Students

Variables	Perception	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal wallis test	df	Asymp. Sig.
Relationship on socio-personal behavior	Very poor perception	1	3.00	7.868	3	0.049*
	Poor perception	18	37.44			
	Good perception	41	36.52			
	Very good perception	17	48.74			
	Total	77				

The statistic in Table 3 indicates that there is statistically significant relationship between perception and impact on socio-personal behaviour (Kruskal Wallis test = 7.868, $p = 0.049$). Further analysis revealed a weak linear relationship between both variables, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of 0.226, $p = 0.049$ (2-sided).

related. This means that, the students generally had a good perception and impact on educational adjustment, both variables were not significantly statistically related.

variables, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of 0.267, $p = 0.019$ (2-sided). This means that, the students generally had a good perception and impact on educational adjustment hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

There is no statistically significant relationship between perception of guidance and counselling and students' educational adjustment (Kruskal Wallis test = 3.992, $p = 0.262$). This means that although the students generally had a good perception and impact

on educational adjustment, both variables were not significantly statistically related. Thus, we do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis Ho1 which states thus: “There is no relationship between students’ perception of guidance and counselling services and their educational adjustment.” In other words, the null hypothesis Ho1 is accepted. This is in line with the study carried out by Mahmud et al (2014).

There is statistically significant relationship between perception and impact on vocation/career choice (Krystal Wallis test = 8.801, $p = 0.032$). Further analysis revealed a weak linear relationship between both variables, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of 0.267, $p = 0.019$ (2-sided). Therefore, we have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis Ho2 which states thus: “There is no relationship between students’ perception of guidance and counselling services and their vocation/career choice.” In other words, the null hypothesis Ho2 is rejected. Thus students with good perception of school guidance and counselling services had better vocation/career choice. This is in agreement with the study carried out by Babatunde and Osakinle (2013).

There is statistically significant relationship between perception and impact on socio-personal behaviour (Krystal Wallis test = 7.868, $p = 0.049$). Further analysis revealed a weak linear relationship between both variables, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of 0.226, $p = 0.049$ (2-sided). Therefore, we have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis Ho3 which states thus: “There is no relationship between students’ perception of guidance and counselling services and their socio-personal behaviour.” In other words, the null hypothesis Ho3 is rejected. Thus, students with good perception of school guidance and counselling services had better socio-personal behaviour. This is

in line with the study carried out by Gatua et al (2015).

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is no relationship between perception of students on the impact of guidance and counselling services and their educational adjustment. Thus, students adjust in school irrespective of guidance and counselling services in school. Furthermore, there is relationship between perception of students on the impact of guidance and counselling services and their vocation/career choice. Thus, students with good perception of school guidance and counselling services had better vocation/career choice. In addition, there is relationship between perception of students on the impact of guidance and counselling services and their socio-personal behavior. Thus, students with good perception of school guidance and counselling services had better socio-personal behaviour.

Recommendations

1. School counsellors should employ viable counselling approaches that would meet the educational needs of the students in order to enable them attain high in their academic achievements.
2. School counsellors in collaboration with relevant stakeholders should occasionally engage the students on career development activities such as career week, excursions, career modelling etc.
3. School guidance and counselling programmes should be made attractive to students by employing the client-centered approaches so that they would develop self-exploratory skills that are necessary for problem solving and persona-social development.

References

- Agi, C. W. (2014). Evaluation of Students’ Perception of School Counselling and Their Attitudes Toward Its Programmes. *Arabian Journal of Business and*

- Management Review (Nigerian Chapter)*, 2(5), 103–110.
- Akinade, E. A., Sokan, B. O. & Osarenren, N. (2005). *An introduction to Guidance and Counselling: A basic text for educational institutions in Nigeria*.
- Babatunde, J. O., & Osakinle, E. O. (2013). Effects of group guidance and counselling techniques on students' vocational maturity in Ekiti state secondary schools, Ekiti state, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(29). Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1524863197?accountid=17242>
- Dabone K. T., Graham Y. A., Fabea I. B. (2015). Impact of Guidance and Counseling on Academic Performance. (Online), 5(8), 2225–484.
- Eliamani, M. P., Richard, M. L., & Peter, B. (2015). Access to guidance and counseling services and its influence on students' school life and career choice, (Online) 3(2), 38–46.
- Federal Government of Nigeria, (2004). *National Policy on Education (Revised Education)*. NERDC. Press.
- Gatua, D. M. (2014). Impact of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students' Social and Emotional Adjustment in Public Urban and Rural Secondary Schools in Nakuru and Uasin Gishu Counties, Kenya, (Online) 3(11), 431–438.
- Gatua, D. M., Sindabi, A. M., & Chepchieng, M. C. (2015). Impact of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students' Behaviour Modification between Selected Public Urban and Rural Secondary Schools in Rift Valley Province, Kenya. (Online), 5(19), 2225–484.
- Ibrahim, R., Aloka, P. J. O., Wambiya, P., & Raburu, P. (2014). Perceptions on the Role of Guidance and Counselling Programme on Kenyan Secondary School Students' Career Decision Making. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 4(6), 313–324. <http://doi.org/10.5901/jesr.2014.v4n6p313>
- Ipaye B. (2015). *Counselling Theories*. National Open University of Nigeria <http://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>.
- Kasomo, D. (2007). *Research Methods in Humanities & Education (Research, Statistics, Measurement, Evaluation & Testing)*. Zapf Chancery.
- Mehmood, A., Rashid, M., & Azeem, M. (2011). Impact of guidance and counseling on academic performance. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(20), 282–288.